

Trace elements in groundwater of granitic terrain : A case study of the Tirupati region, Southern India

Rama Mohan Kurakalva*, Keshav Krishna Aradhi and Bipinkumar Gedam

Environmental Geochemistry Group, CSIR-National Geophysical Research Institute, Uppal Road, Hyderabad-500 007, India

E-mail : krngri@rediffmail.com Fax : 91-40-23434651

Abstract : The trace elemental composition and their distribution trends in groundwater over Gajulamandyam watershed of granitic terrain, Tirupati region is investigated. Groundwater samples are collected from different bore wells in the vicinity of the study area. The physicochemical parameters of groundwater were measured *in situ*. Trace elemental concentrations were determined using inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). Results reveal that groundwater from Gajulamandyam watershed is very well controlled by trace elements like Al, As, B, Ba, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Mn, Ni, Pb, Se and Zn are within the permissible limits according to WHO guidelines for drinking water except for Ca, Mg and Sr. The concentration of calcium, magnesium and strontium are found above the permissible limits in ground water of study area. The elevated concentration of these alkaline earth elements in ground water shows that the study area is contaminated with common source of geogenic origin rather than anthropogenic influence.

Keywords : Trace elements, groundwater, granitic terrain, source of pollution.

Introduction

Rapid increase in anthropogenic activity due to industrialization, urbanization and overexploitation of water resources, their impact on human health and environment are major concern. Eventually, quantification and understanding the chemistry of ground water with respect to trace elements is essential. The anomalous distribution of trace elements in hydrological system and possible pathway depending on the environmental parameters, for instance each element moves at different rate due to the changing environment^{1,2}. The trace elements in ground water and surface water depend on natural factors such as the geology of the aquifer, the types of interaction between water and aquifer^{3,4}. On the other hand, human activities like use of fertilizers, pesticides and insecticide in agriculture, waste chemicals from industries and sewage of urban as well as rural areas can alter the delicate groundwater system^{4,5}. Therefore, study on trace elements composition in ground water is vital in order to ascertain the impact of anthropogenic and geogenic influence on water environment. The present work describes the trace elements concentrations in groundwater from a watershed of granitic terrain which is surrounded by an

upcoming industrial area and large habitat lying on banks of Swarnamukhi river. Literature survey reveals that no data is available on the groundwater quality of Gajulamandyam watershed with respect to trace elemental studies to the best of our knowledge. The objective of study is to determine the concentrations of trace elements in ground water and provide hydrochemistry baseline data with respect to water quality, a major concern for public health.

Materials and methods :

Study area :

Gajulamandyam watershed is lying on the banks of Swarnamukhi river located in Chittoor district of Andhra Pradesh, India. The drainage of the area is controlled by Swarnamukhi river which flows from west to east and elevation varies between 100 to 120 m above MSL subsequently the groundwater flow following the geomorphology of the area. The latitude and longitude of the study area is from 13°35'N-13°32'N to 79°29'E-79°34'E (Fig. 1). The watershed comprises of fast growing industrial park includes manufacturing and processing industries like sugar, ceramic, beverages and pharmaceuticals surrounded with large residential areas. This study area

Fig. 1. Location map of the study area with sampling stations.

has been chosen because of steady increasing of anthropogenic inputs and no data available needs the investigation of environmental geochemical studies for further management of water resources.

The study area has composed of Peninsular Gneiss in basement, Bairenkonda Quartzite and Cumbum formation which belongs to Cuddapah super group overlain to basement and then recent alluvium⁶. Rocks in the study area have noticed joints, fractures and other structural features. These parameters are important in understanding of groundwater movement and its distribution, interacting with water⁷.

Analytical methodology :

Groundwater (12) samples from representative stations

located in the vicinity of the study area were collected in clean polyethylene bottles by following sampling routine set for water quality studies⁸. The pH, EC and TDS of water samples were measured *in situ* using portable meters (Eutech Instruments-model pH Tester10, ECTester11⁺ and TDSTester11⁺ respectively). All water samples were analyzed for trace elements concentrations of Al, As, B, Ba, Ca, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Mg, Mn, Ni, Pb, Se, Sr and Zn using Perkin-Elmer SCIEX (Model ELAN DRC II) Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometer (ICP-MS). The sample introduction system consisted of standard Meinhard nebulizer with a cyclonic spray chamber attached to an auto sampler (CETAC ASX-500). All quantitative measurements were performed using instrument software.

Results and discussion

Analytical data of groundwater samples pertain to the physicochemical parameters and descriptive statistics of trace elemental concentrations are presented in Table 1. The data obtained for groundwater are discussed according to the WHO guideline values as well as Indian Standard Specifications (ISI) in order to ascertain the suitability of water for various purposes.

to 2745.6 mg/L with an average value of 1261.33 mg/L indicating higher concentration than the permissible limits according to WHO guideline values and ISI desirable values. Apparently, these data indicating that water resources in the study area could be classified as hard water not fit for consumption as drinking water.

Trace element concentrations :

The ground water samples collected in the study area

Table 1. Physicochemical and trace elemental concentrations of groundwater of Gajulamandyam water shed, Tirupati region, India

Parameters	Min	Max	Average	SD	WHO ^a guideline value	BIS ^b	
						Highest desirable value	Maximum permissible limit
pH	7.3	8.4	7.79	0.32	6.5-8.5	6.5-8.5	No relaxation
EC (µS/cm)	1131	4290	1970.83	906.78	1500	n/a	n/a
TDS (mg/L)	723.84	2745.6	1261.33	580.34	< 1000	500	2000
Al (mg/L)	0.0003	0.0013	0.0008	0.0003	0.2	0.03	0.2
As (mg/L)	0.0009	0.0275	0.0078	0.0085	0.01	0.05	No relaxation
B (mg/L)	0.0836	0.2931	0.1864	0.0768	0.3	1	5
Ba (mg/L)	0.0065	0.1467	0.0508	0.0400	0.7	n/a	n/a
Ca (mg/L)	8.52	234.85	80.44	58.89	75	75	200
Cd (mg/L)	0.0000	0.0001	0.0001	0.0000	0.03	0.01	No relaxation
Co (mg/L)	0.0001	0.0010	0.0003	0.0002	0.1	0.1	0.1
Cr (mg/L)	0.0049	0.0137	0.0067	0.0024	0	0.05	No relaxation
Cu (mg/L)	0.0022	0.1300	0.0192	0.0352	0.1	0.05	1.5
Fe (mg/L)	0.0174	0.3055	0.1138	0.0755	0.3	0.3	1
Mg (mg/L)	0.00	65.27	36.73	23.26	50	30	100
Mn (mg/L)	0.0020	0.1994	0.0483	0.0561	0.1	0.1	0.3
Ni (mg/L)	0.0003	0.0104	0.0032	0.0026	0.02	0.1	0.3
Pb (mg/L)	0.0000	0.0032	0.0004	0.0009	0.01	0.05	No relaxation
Se (mg/L)	0.0017	0.0306	0.0091	0.0078	0	0.01	No relaxation
Sr (mg/L)	0.1415	1.8796	0.9026	0.4935	0.07	n/a	n/a
Zn (mg/L)	0.0135	0.9059	0.3134	0.3219	3	5	15

n/a : Not available.

^aWHO : World Health Organization.

^bBIS : Bureau of Indian Standards.

Physicochemical parameters :

The pH of groundwater samples found in the range of 7.3 to 8.4 in groundwater which was measured *in situ* in order to avoid variations of pH value due to escape of CO₂ as reported in the literature⁹. Results indicating that the pH varies from neutral to slightly alkaline which are within desirable limits. Electrical conductivity values ranged from 1131 to 4290 µS/cm in groundwater of the study area. TDS values are found in the range of 723.84

is ascribed as GGW (i.e. Ganjulamandyam ground water) from number 1 to 13. Table 2 showed the trace elements concentration in groundwater of the study area. The data obtained has been classified and discussed in different groups namely, toxic elements (Pb and As), alkaline earths (Sr, Ba, Ca and Mg), transition metals (Mn, Co and Ni), metallic elements (Cu, Cd, Fe, Zn and Cr) and other non-metallic elements (B, Se and Al). Human health effects of different class of trace elements in groundwater

Table 2. Distribution of trace elemental concentrations (mg/L) in groundwater

Sample ID	Al	As	B	Ba	Ca	Cd	Co	Cr	Cu	Fe	Mg	Mn	Ni	Pb	Se	Sr	Zn
GGW-1	0.0010	0.0175	0.2651	0.0587	33.62	0.0000	0.0002	0.0060	0.0080	0.0503	48.36	0.0112	0.0015	0.0001	0.0078	0.5871	0.0246
GGW-2	0.0012	0.0045	0.0836	0.0099	27.30	0.0000	0.0003	0.0064	0.0139	0.0580	24.47	0.0749	0.0014	0.0001	0.0019	0.4316	0.1552
GGW-3	0.0005	0.0009	0.1145	0.0360	97.10	0.0001	0.0002	0.0066	0.0108	0.1212	48.29	0.0310	0.0034	0.0000	0.0030	0.7573	0.2504
GGW-4	0.0004	0.0010	0.0875	0.0153	60.94	0.0000	0.0002	0.0137	0.0022	0.0831	48.51	0.1994	0.0018	0.0000	0.0017	0.6577	0.1211
GGW-5	0.0011	0.0011	0.1117	0.0739	83.17	0.0001	0.0001	0.0057	0.0070	0.1050	48.89	0.0035	0.0026	0.0000	0.0027	0.8559	0.9059
GGW-6	0.0010	0.0040	0.2026	0.0077	89.45	0.0001	0.0002	0.0071	0.0079	0.1152	62.28	0.0200	0.0032	0.0001	0.0113	1.2129	0.8182
GGW-7	0.0008	0.0182	0.2750	0.0624	34.75	0.0000	0.0002	0.0053	0.0091	0.0544	49.48	0.0117	0.0016	0.0001	0.0081	0.6075	0.0375
GGW-8	0.0013	0.0275	0.2931	0.0065	8.52	0.0001	0.0001	0.0055	0.0109	0.0174	6.48	0.0020	0.0003	0.0032	0.0114	0.1415	0.4164
GGW-9	0.0005	0.0045	0.1628	0.1467	104.07	0.0000	0.0006	0.0057	0.1300	0.1496	65.27	0.0383	0.0052	0.0005	0.0306	1.2494	0.1621
GGW-10	0.0005	0.0064	0.2166	0.0741	234.85	0.0001	0.0010	0.0081	0.0205	0.3055	0.00	0.0772	0.0104	0.0003	0.0115	1.8796	0.7097
GGW-12	0.0003	0.0024	0.2634	0.0562	84.33	0.0000	0.0003	0.0053	0.0060	0.1687	38.75	0.0227	0.0032	0.0001	0.0113	0.8868	0.1458
GGW-13	0.0007	0.0051	0.1608	0.0621	107.20	0.0001	0.0004	0.0049	0.0043	0.1376	0.00	0.0878	0.0036	0.0004	0.0081	1.5638	0.0135

are described in Table 3. Among the trace elements, alkaline earths Sr, Ca and Mg were found in elevated concentrations.

The concentration of Strontium (Sr) was found exceeding permissible limit of 0.07 mg/L (WHO 1984) throughout the study area. The Sr concentration was observed in the range of 0.1414 to 1.8795 mg/L in groundwater with an average of 0.9025 mg/L. Spatial distribution of Strontium in groundwater is shown in Fig. 2 reveals that Sr is high at the place of confluence of river than the other area under study. The Sr in groundwater might be due to leaching of Sr containing wastage from industries. It is observed that concentration of Sr has distributed in the study area from west to east direction may be due to river flow direction and also regional slope of area.

The high concentration of Sr is evident that the source could be anthropogenic due to the overexploitation of groundwater, industrial waste and fertilizer uses in agricultural field. Further, it was observed that an input of strontium in groundwater because of extend geology e.g. rocks like granite, sand stone gneiss, schist etc. of the study area. This may be due to natural recrystallization of rocks and weathering of rocks and soils^{13,14}. It has been reported¹⁵ in the literature that Sr content could be linked to classify water in coastal aquifers as concentration of Sr is < 1.6 mg/L as fresh groundwater, 1.6–5.0 mg/L as brackish water and > 5.0 mg/L as saline groundwater. Accordingly, results obtained in the present investigation have been tried classify groundwater. Based on this, it is observed that the all groundwater samples fall under the category of fresh groundwater. Nevertheless, few of groundwater samples Sr concentrations (~ 1.879 mg/L) fall under brackish water category which are unfit for the drinking. It is further explained that an increase of salinity of ground water will be observed in future as the overexploitation of groundwater and discharges from industrial waste and fertilizer uses in agricultural field also increase simultaneously.

It is well known that elevated concentrations of Sr and Ca in groundwater, absorb by the human beings while consumed water as strontium is coexist with calcium. This is due to the sufficient chemical similarities in both the elements. On the other hand, there is a good correlation between Sr and Ca in ground water indicating that the

Table 3. Trace elements classification and their effects on human health

Classification	Health effects	Cited reference
Toxic elements :		
Pb (mg/L)	It is toxic to the central and peripheral nervous systems, including subencephalopathic neurological and behavioral effects. Its consumption in higher quantity may cause hearing loss, blood disorders, and hypertension eventually; it may prove to be fatal.	10, 11
As (mg/L)	Excess amount of arsenic in water causes skin damage or problems with circulatory systems, and may have increased risk of getting cancer.	16
Alkaline earths :		
Sr (mg/L)	Strontium is known to have a pronounced rachitic effect.	16
Ba (mg/L)	Excess concentration of barium in water may cause to increase in blood pressure in human beings.	16
Ca (mg/L)	It prevents the absorption of heavy metal in the body, and increase bone mass at lower concentrations whereas high concentration of calcium in water may adversely affect the absorption of other essential minerals in the body.	16
Mg (mg/L)	It is an essential element in cardiac and vascular function, but in drinking water may have a laxative effect particularly with magnesium sulphate concentration above 700 mg/L.	16
Transition metals :		
Ni (mg/L)	Decrease body weight, heart and liver damage, and skin irritation.	10
Co (mg/L)	Health effects may be caused by radiation of radioactive cobalt isotopes. This can cause sterility, hair loss, vomiting, bleeding, diarrhea, coma and even death.	9, 16
Mn (mg/L)	Large doses cause headaches, apathy, irritability, insomnia, and weakness of the legs. Long-term heavy exposure may result in a nervous system disorder.	10
Metallic elements :		
Al (mg/L)	It is the most abundant metal in the earth's crust and therefore is likely to be present at some level in most ground water. The correlation of aluminum consumption to nervous system disorders is currently being researched.	10
Cu (mg/L)	Copper is an essential element for enzyme activity but excessive doses may affect on central nervous system, and cause the depression.	10
Cd (mg/L)	Cadmium is biologically a non-essential, non-beneficial element known to have a high toxic potential and cause kidney damage.	9
Zn (mg/L)	Zinc deficiency may leads to dwarfism, dermatitis and loss of taste.	9
Fe (mg/L)	Iron in water is not a health hazard by itself but it may increase the hazard of pathogenic organisms, since many of these organisms require iron to grow.	10
Cr (mg/L)	High concentration of Cr in groundwater may cause ulceration of nasal septum, dermatitis and liver or kidney damage and gastrointestinal disorders.	19
Non-metallic elements :		
B (mg/L)	Long-term exposure of humans to boron compounds leads to mild gastrointestinal irritation.	9
Se (mg/L)	Hair or fingernail loss; numbness in fingers or toes; circulatory problems.	16

source of contamination of these alkaline earths in to the study area (Fig. 3a). Strontium was known to have a pronounced rachitic effect¹⁶.

Barium (Ba) concentration in the groundwater of study area is in the range of 0.007 to 0.147 mg/L that are below the WHO permissible limit of 0.7 mg/L. Excess

concentration of barium in water may cause to increase in blood pressure in human beings.

Calcium (Ca) is one of the most abundant elements in water, which prevents the absorption of heavy metal in the body, and increase bone mass at lower concentrations whereas high concentration of calcium in water may ad-

Fig. 2. Contour map of alkaline earths in groundwater.

versely affect the absorption of other essential minerals in the body. Concentration of Ca found in the groundwater contain in the range of 8.52 to 234.85 mg/L of the study area. All groundwater samples are found high concentration of calcium than the permissible limit¹⁷.

Magnesium (Mg) is an essential element in cardiac and vascular function, but in drinking water may have a laxative effect particularly with magnesium sulphate con-

centration above 700 mg/L. However, the human body tends to alter to these laxative effects with time. Mg concentrations were found in the range of below detection limit (BDL) to 65.27 mg/L which are below permissible limit¹⁶ of 50 mg/L except at two stations (i.e. sites 6 and 9).

Elemental interrelationship :

A cross correlation chart was prepared in order to visualize the correlation between the different trace ele-

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Fig. 3. Scatter plots of trace elements in groundwater.

ments which are shown in Table 4 for groundwater samples. In this study, those trace elements with correlation value higher than 0.50 were taken in to account for interpretation of correlation matrix. Correlation of Sr with the other trace elements such as Ca ($r = 0.82$), Fe ($r = 0.76$), Ni ($r = 0.75$), Co ($r = 0.62$) and found in groundwater samples are correlated as illustrated in Fig. 3(a)

(b), (c), (d). Transition elements like nickel and cobalt in groundwater samples have good positive correlation for Ni ($r = 0.92$) and Co ($r = 0.75$) with Fe as shown in Fig. 3(e) and (f). These correlations suggested that the trace elements contamination of groundwater in this study is due to natural origin rather than anthropogenic influence.

Table 4. Cross-correlation between the different trace elements in groundwater

	Al	As	B	Ba	Ca	Cd	Co	Cr	Cu	Fe	Mg	Mn	Ni	Pb	Se	Sr	Zn
Al	1.00																
As	0.53	1.00															
B	0.75	1.00	1.00														
Ba	0.06	0.06	1.00	1.00													
Ca	0.42	0.11	0.42	1.00	1.00												
Cd	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00											
Co	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00										
Cr	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.05	1.00	1.00									
Cu	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	1.00								
Fe	0.44	0.44	0.44	0.44	0.44	0.44	0.44	0.44	0.44	1.00							
Mg	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.97	1.00						
Mn	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00					
Ni	0.87	0.87	0.87	0.87	0.87	0.87	0.87	0.87	0.87	0.87	0.87	0.87	1.00				
Pb	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.21	1.00			
Se	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00		
Sr	0.79	0.79	0.79	0.79	0.79	0.79	0.79	0.79	0.79	0.79	0.79	0.79	0.79	0.79	0.79	1.00	
Zn	0.41	0.41	0.41	0.41	0.41	0.41	0.41	0.41	0.41	0.41	0.41	0.41	0.41	0.41	0.41	0.41	1.00

Conclusions

The elevated concentration of alkaline earth elements such as Ca, Mg and Sr in groundwater shows that the study area is contaminated with common source of geogenic origin. This study further suggests that the water resources in the area are hard and saline not suitable for drinking purpose. The environmental geochemical studies provide a baseline data with respect to water pollution which could be further useful to evaluate the anthropogenic influence on water resources.

Recommendations

The present investigation showed elevated a concentration of Sr is observed than the permissible limit. Therefore, a simple treatment procedure is recommended in order to protect human health in the study area. Strontium can be removed from with strong acid cation exchange resin. It can be in sodium form as in a water softener or the hydrogen form as in the cation portion of two-column deionizer. Reverse Osmosis (RO) will also reduce strontium but as stated above strontium sulphate can be a RO membrane foulant.

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